

SUSTAINABLE TRAVEL CHOICES: A STUDY OF ALTERNATIVE TOURISM IN NORTH SULAWESI

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Abstract

As the demand for more responsible tourism practices grows, alternative tourism emerges for its potential to drive sustainable impacts. This study explores the factors influencing the intention to visit alternative tourism in North Sulawesi, a concept promoted for its positive impact within responsible tourism. Employing a quantitative survey method with incidental sampling, the research analyzes data using inferential statistics. Key findings reveal that destination attractiveness and travel motivation have a significant impact on the intention to visit, while destination image and novelty seeking behavior do not directly affect the intention to visit. Destination attractiveness and destination image significantly influence novelty seeking behavior, but neither of them influences the intention to visit when mediated by novelty seeking behavior. Destination image has a significant effect on both travel motivation and intention to visit, either directly or mediated by travel motivation, while destination attractiveness shows no significant impact on either. The findings emphasize the relationship between psychological factors, such as motivation and novelty-seeking, and perceptual elements, such as destination image and attractiveness. While destination image and travel motivation shape the travel intentions, destination attractiveness and novelty-seeking behavior have a more secondary or supportive influence.

Keywords: Intention to Visit, Destination Image, Destination Attractiveness, Travel Motivation, Novelty Seeking Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism promotes economic growth, prompting continued efforts to strengthen it. Yet, poorly managed tourism can have detrimental effects on natural resources. Overcrowding, pollution, and overexploitation of ecosystems are the results from unregulated tourism, leading to habitat destruction and loss of biodiversity. To balance economic benefits with environmental protection, sustainable tourism practices are essential. Sustainable tourism is developed from a sustainability concept that concerns long-term benefits for the environment, society, and economy. It aims to minimize the negative impacts of tourism while maximizing benefits for local communities, ecosystems, and future generations. Empirical studies show that sustainable tourism practices play a vital role in minimizing negative impacts on local communities and the environment (Ibnou-Laaroussi, et al., 2020; Abreu et al., 2024). Alternative tourism is regarded for its role in promoting responsible tourism practices. It plays a significant part in achieving sustainable tourism by promoting and encouraging environmentally friendly activities, supporting local economies, and preserving cultural heritage. Alternative tourism refers to non-traditional tourism that focuses on unique and authentic experiences, often involving interaction with local culture, traditions, and the environment (Isaac & Eid, 2018). This type of tourism arose as a result of the negative effects of conventional tourism, such as

environmental damage or cultural degradation. People's desire to try something new and have a unique tourism experience also drives the development of alternative tourism. The extent to which tourists engage in alternative tourism is influenced by numerous factors, among which the intention to visit is. The absence of intention will result in someone not visiting a tourist attraction. Most tourists will visit popular /mass tourist destinations because it offers more diverse activities, interesting experiences, affordable prices, well-known places, convenience and accessibility, and many more. Alternative tourism is seen as niche or specific activities, unfamiliar environments leading to safety concerns, not for budget-conscious travelers, but offers unique and authentic experiences.

North Sulawesi is one of Indonesia's designated to be environmentally friendly tourism. North Sulawesi has many tourist attractions such as environmental, cultural, and culinary tourism including alternative tourism such as maritime tourism, community-based tourism, sports tourism, and ecotourism. The Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 16 of 2024 addressing the Manado-Likupang National Tourism Destination Master Plan for 2023-2044 specifies alternative tourism in North Sulawesi. Earlier studies on alternative tourism have been conducted across various regions in Indonesia, exploring it within diverse contexts, however, study specifically examining alternative tourism in North Sulawesi remains relevant even though there have been similar studies because of the unique potential of its tourism which has not been fully explored in the context of alternative tourism and encourages more in-depth local studies. In North Sulawesi, alternative tourism is often considered less popular than mainstream tourism because tourists may not be aware of these lesser-known destinations. Mainstream tourism trends dominate social media and influence traveler behavior. The convenience and ease of mainstream tourism outweigh the unique experiences offered by alternative options. Mainstream tourism destinations comfort tourist with established infrastructure, well-maintained facilities, and predictable experiences. Furthermore, unlike conventional tourism destinations, alternative tourism is marketed as eco-friendly and community-focused that involves higher costs due to smaller-scale operations and sustainable practices.

This study emphasizes novelty-seeking behavior and travel motivation linked to the intention to visit a destination. Alternative tourism encourages novelty-seeking tourists to experience something new, unique, and different from the usual tourist environment. Travel motivation underlines the reason for an individual's decision to choose a particular type of tourism, such as alternative tourism. When alternative tourism aligns with tourists' novelty seeker and travel motivation, it increases the likelihood of choosing it. Thus, this study contribute to the understanding the intention to visit alternative tourism.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Intention To Visit

Intention to visit represents an individual's interest or willingness to travel to a particular destination. It serves as a key predictor of actual travel behavior and reflects the traveler's anticipation of the experience they expect to have. The intention to visit can be understood as

the perceived probability to travel to a specific destination within a designated timeframe (Woodside & Lysonski, 1989).

Destination image refers to the perception or mental impression tourists hold about a particular travel destination, regardless of whether they have personally visited it. This perception can be influenced by various sources, such as media, advertisements, word of mouth, or personal research. A positive destination image can significantly enhance tourists' interest and likelihood of visiting, as it fosters feelings of excitement and trust. Conversely, a negative image, shaped by factors like poor reviews or safety concerns, can lower the desire to travel to that location. Chalip et al. (2003) found that destination image significantly influences the intention to visit.

H1: The image of a destination significantly influences the intention to visit.

Destination attractiveness refers to various elements or characteristics that draw tourists and make it appealing for visitation. It includes natural landscapes, cultural significance, amenities, activities, and others that entice visitors to explore the destination. A destination's attractiveness, particularly with distinctive characteristics, generates a strong intention to visit. In other words, the more attractive a destination appears in terms of its unique offerings and experiences, the higher the likelihood of tourists planning to visit. Yacob, Johannes, and Qomariyah (2019) revealed a positive influence between destination attractiveness and visiting intention.

H2: Destination attractiveness significantly affects the intention to visit.

In the context of tourism, novelty-seeking behavior refers to a tourist's inclination to seek new, unique, and unfamiliar experiences when choosing travel destinations. The perception that a destination offers new and exciting experiences enhances the likelihood that novelty-seeking tourists will intend to visit. Such tourists are more likely to have a higher intention to visit destination that promise to fulfill their desire for novelty and escape from routine. Novelty-seeking has a significant effect on behavior intention (Pujiastuti, et al., 2020).

H3: Novelty-seeking behavior has a significant impact on the intention to visit a destination.

Travel motivation determines whether or not tourists will visit a particular destination. When a person is motivated to travel due to certain needs, the intention to visit a destination emerges as a response to fulfilling those needs. The stronger the alignment between a destination's offerings and a tourist's motivations whether for relaxation, exploration, or adventure, the higher the intention to visit that location. On the other hand, if a destination fails to meet the tourist motivations then their intention to visit may decrease, even if the destination is generally appealing. Sukhragchaa et al. (2024) found that push motivation do not impact the intention to travel but pull motivation has a significant effect on travel intention. Chi & Phuong (2022) found that tourists' travel motivations is significantly and positively associated with their intention to visit city tourism.

H4: The motivation to travel significantly impacts the intention to visit a destination.

Travel Motivation

Travel motivation refers to the underlying reasons or desires that compel individuals to seek out travel experiences. These motivations can be intrinsic, such as the need for relaxation, adventure, or the excitement of novelty, or they can be external, including factors like the appeal of a destination, its convenience, accessibility, and what it has to offer.

Destination image plays a role in shaping travel motivation because it is the initial point of contact between tourists and the destination. Tourist travel motivation is driven by the desire to visit a destination formed from images and impressions about the tourist destination through direct information, the media, or people's experiences. Therefore, tourist destinations with a positive image tend to motivate travel more strongly among tourists. Apart from that, when the image of the destination matches tourists' desires, the motivation to visit will be higher, such as eco tourists who are more motivated to visit ecotourism than non-eco tourists. This suggests that a destination's image that resonates with specific interests or values can significantly enhance the intention to visit. Chi & Pham (2024) identified that the image of an eco-destination significantly enhances the influence of four key travel motivations—excitement, escape, knowledge-seeking, and self-development—on individuals' intention to engage in ecotourism.

H5: Destination Image significantly influences Travel Motivation.

A tourist destination that is attractive to travelers, whether in terms of natural beauty, facilities, or the experiences it offers, is more likely to motivate tourists to visit. A destination's appeal that aligns with the emotional or physical needs of travelers strengthens their motivation to travel. On the other hand, if a destination lacks the appeal that aligns with the needs or expectations of tourists, it can diminish their motivation to travel there.

H6: Destination Attractiveness significantly influences Travel Motivation

Novelty Seeking Behavior

Tourism provides an opportunity to escape from life's problems (McIntosh and Goeldner 1986). The concept of escape has been related to the relaxation and enjoyment that tourism offers, which can help relieve stress and improve mental well-being. In contrast to mass tourism, where familiarity and comfort are prioritized, novelty seekers prefer to engage in local traditions, untouched environments, or unconventional activities. Destination image shapes how tourists perceive and experience a destination. For tourists with a tendency to seek novelty, a destination's unique and distinct image becomes a primary motivator for visiting. These tourists are not only interested in well-known or popular destinations but are more inclined to explore places offering experiences they have not encountered before, which can provide a sense of novelty, uniqueness, or a different perspective. Therefore, a destination image that promises authentic experiences, adventure, or cultural diversity encourages novelty-seeking behavior, as it aligns with the tourists' desire for deeper and more distinct experiences.

H7: Destination Image significantly influences Novelty Seeking behavior

Tourists who are eager to discover new experiences are often driven by the attractions of destinations that offer unique and different things from what they usually encounter. These attractions are not limited to physical or natural sites but also include social and emotional aspects presented by the destination, which allow tourists to experience something profound and distinct. Therefore, destinations that possess the ability to offer unique, different experiences that spark curiosity will further strengthen the novelty-seeking behavior of tourists. This behavior is not only related to physical exploration but also to the search for deeper experiences that can enrich their lives.

H8: Destination Attractiveness significantly influences Novelty Seeking behavior

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research adopts a survey methodology underpinned by a quantitative approach. Designed as an explanatory study, it seeks to investigate the relationships between variables to identify the factors influencing public interest in alternative tourism within North Sulawesi. The analysis targets the local community as the primary unit of observation. A sample of 250 respondents was selected using a simple random sampling technique, ensuring equal representation across the population. Data collection utilized both physical questionnaires and online forms distributed via Google Forms. The dataset was analyzed using Partial Least Square (PLS), a robust variance-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique. This method facilitates simultaneous evaluation of the measurement model, which tests validity and reliability, and the structural model, which assesses causal relationships and predictive hypotheses.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The study's findings include a detailed review of the measurement model, an analysis of the structural model, and an in-depth exploration of the results

Table 1: Validity and Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (rho_a)	Composite Reliability (rho_c)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Destination Attractiveness	0.828	0.834	0.897	0.744
Destination Image	0.826	0.842	0.896	0.743
Intention to Visit	0.713	0.727	0.836	0.630
Novelty Seeking	0.755	0.775	0.860	0.674
Travel Motivation	0.686	0.762	0.860	0.755

Source: Processed Data

The AVE (Average Variance Extracted) for all variables is above 0.5, indicating that each indicator effectively represents its corresponding variable through strong convergent validity. Similarly, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) values for all variables exceed 0.6, signifying high internal consistency and reliability. These results validate that the constructs and indicators used in the study are both reliable and valid, making them suitable for accurately measuring the intended variables.

Table 2: Determination Coefficient Results

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Intention to Visit	0.769	0.754
Novelty Seeking	0.670	0.668
Travel Motivation	0.436	0.432

Source: Processed Data

The R-Square values indicate that Destination Image and Destination Attractiveness explain 76.9% of Intention to Visit, 67% of Novelty Seeking Behavior, and 43.6% of Travel Motivation, with the remaining percentages influenced by external factors. Combined, these variables, along with Novelty Seeking Behavior and Travel Motivation, account for 76.9% of Intention to Visit, leaving 23.1% attributable to variables outside the model.

Table 3: Fit Model

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.077	0.078
d ULS	0.987	1,016
d G	0.517	0.541
Chi-Square	744,663	761,888
NFI	0.923	0.914

Source: Processed Data

The output reveals an SRMS value of 0.077, which is below the threshold of 0.08, and an NFI value of 0.987, surpassing the 0.900 mark. To ensure fit model, indicators must satisfy the criteria of SRMS < 0.08 and NFI > 0.90. Given that both conditions are met, it can be concluded that the model satisfies the adequacy criteria and is effective in illustrating the relationships between the variables.

Table 4: Direct Effect Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Destination Attractiveness -> Intention to Visit	0.226	0.229	0.069	3.290	0.001
Destination Attractiveness -> Novelty Seeking	0.087	0.088	0.040	2.155	0.031
Destination Attractiveness -> Travel Motivation	0.080	0.082	0.052	1,536	0.125
Destination Image -> Intention to Visit	0.141	0.152	0.136	1,033	0.302
Destination Image -> Novelty Seeking	0.787	0.787	0.042	18,678	0.000
Destination Image -> Travel Motivation	0.630	0.631	0.048	13,099	0.000
Novelty Seeking -> Intention to Visit	0.037	0.042	0.152	0.241	0.809
Travel Motivation -> Intention to Visit	0.221	0.228	0.100	2.201	0.028

Source: Processed Data

The output indicates that certain direct effects have a p-value below 0.05, signifying statistical significance, while others have a p-value exceeding 0.05, suggesting they are not statistically significant.

Table 5: Indirect Effect Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Destination Image -> Novelty Seeking -> Intention to Visit	0.029	0.034	0.121	0.238	0.812
Destination Attractiveness -> Travel Motivation -> Intention to Visit	0.018	0.020	0.017	1,066	0.287
Destination Image -> Travel Motivation -> Intention to Visit	0.139	0.144	0.065	2.141	0.032
Destination Attractiveness -> Novelty Seeking -> Intention to Visit	0.003	0.003	0.014	0.220	0.826

Source: Processed Data

The output shows that three indirect relationships between variables have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating they are not statistically significant. In contrast, one indirect relationship has a p-value below 0.05, confirming its statistical significance.

Figure 1: Structural Model (Inner Model)

Figure 1 illustrates a model that highlights the interconnected relationships between destination image, destination attractiveness, novelty seeking behavior, travel motivation, and intention to visit.

Discussion

The findings demonstrate that destination attractiveness and travel motivation significantly shape intentions to visit alternative tourism destinations. Attractiveness influences tourists' decision-making by affecting their emotions, expectations, and behavioral intentions, with highly attractive destinations more likely to be chosen than those perceived as less appealing (Henkel et al., 2006; Kim & Perdue, 2011). Destinations that emphasize sustainability, community involvement, and responsible tourism practices also strengthen tourists' willingness to visit. This aligns with Ma, Hsiao, and Gao (2017), who found that attractiveness had a stronger impact on travel intention among Chinese students than Indian students.

Travel motivation is equally important, as alternative tourism appeals to individuals seeking cultural exploration, unconventional experiences, or environmentally conscious travel. Prior studies confirm this role, showing that cultural motivations influence participation in cultural activities (Douglas et al., 2024) and health and wellness motivations positively predict behavioral intentions (Gan et al., 2023).

Destination attractiveness and image also contribute to novelty-seeking behavior, particularly in the context of alternative tourism. Attractive destinations and strong images encourage tourists to pursue new and unique experiences that offer a sense of discovery or “first-time” encounters. For alternative tourists, destinations associated with authenticity, cultural preservation, or environmental sustainability become powerful motivators.

However, this study finds that destination image and novelty seeking do not directly influence visit intention. While a positive image is often assumed to drive visitation, practical constraints such as cost, time, or personal misalignment may override such perceptions (Chen & Tsai, 2007). Similarly, novelty-seeking behavior, though driven by curiosity or the desire for new experiences, does not necessarily translate into visit intention if the novelty offered is available elsewhere or fails to match individual preferences (Ayдын, Erdogan, & Koc, 2022).

In the context of alternative tourism, destination image proves more important than attractiveness in shaping travel motivation. Unlike in mass tourism, where attractiveness is a central driver, alternative tourists prioritize authenticity, cultural immersion, and eco-conscious values. Even destinations with limited physical appeal may attract visitors if they align with these values. Importantly, the findings reveal that destination image and attractiveness do not significantly affect visit intention when mediated by novelty-seeking behavior.

Tourists motivated by novelty often pursue diverse and challenging experiences across various destinations rather than relying solely on image or attractiveness. Finally, this study shows that destination image exerts a significant effect on visit intention when mediated by travel motivation.

Positive perceptions enhance motivation, which in turn strengthens the likelihood of visiting. This is consistent with Chi and Pham (2024), who found that eco-destination image amplifies the effects of key motivations—excitement, escape, knowledge-seeking, and self-development—on ecotourism intentions.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings highlight the importance of destination attractiveness and image, mediated by novelty-seeking behavior and travel motivation, in shaping intentions to visit alternative tourism destinations. While attractiveness and motivation significantly influence tourists' decisions, neither destination image nor novelty seeking directly predicts visit intention. Although attractiveness and image encourage novelty-seeking behavior, this pathway does not translate into intention. Instead, destination image plays a more decisive role by enhancing travel motivation, which subsequently increases visit intention, whereas physical attractiveness alone has no direct effect unless supported by motivation.

This study is context-specific to alternative tourism in North Sulawesi and may not be generalizable to other tourism types or regions with different cultural, economic, or environmental settings. Future research could therefore compare alternative tourism in North Sulawesi with similar destinations elsewhere to identify competitive advantages. Moreover, integrating qualitative approaches would provide richer insights into tourists' motivations and intentions, complementing the quantitative evidence presented here.

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